

Grant Agreement 101079792, RESILIENCE PPP

Detailed Organisational Plan (DOP)

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00.03	16/12/2022	DRAFT	WP6 Revised Text	Changes in WBS tables, addition of glossary items
01.00	23/12/2023	FINAL	SCC and BoD suggestions	Modification of the list of objectives according to current developments; Addition of SCC and BoD proposals for glossary

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
DOP	Detailed Organisational Plan
BoD	Board of Directors
CDEP	Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan
CDE	Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation
DMP	Data Management Plan
GA	Grant Agreement
GenA	General Assembly
M	Month
PC	Project Coordinator
PP	Preparatory Phase
PPP	Preparatory Phase Project
REA	European Research Executive Agency
RI	Research Infrastructure
SSC	Service Coordination Committee
TM	Team Member(s)
TNA	Trans-National Access
WP	Work Package
WU	Work Unit

List of Partner Acronyms

Acronym	Partner
FSCIRE	FSCIRE (Coordinator)
BIU	Bar Ilan University
CINECA	CINECA
EPHE	École Pratique des Hautes Études
INFAI	InfAI
KU Leuven	KU Leuven
TUA	Theological University of Apeldoorn
AU-UFO	Albanian University
UNISOFIA	Sofia University
UNSA	University of Sarajevo
UNIWARSAW	University of Warsaw
VOLOS	Volos Academy for Theological Studies
WWU	University of Münster

1. Document overview

1.1. Objective

The European Research Executive Agency (REA) signed a Grant Agreement (GA) with the RESILIENCE Preparatory Phase Project (PPP) consortium. The main aim of the RESILIENCE PPP is to bring RESILIENCE, a European Research Infrastructure on Religious Studies, to the completion of its Preparatory Phase, which started in 2021 and will end in 2025. The work includes legal, governance, financial, technical, strategic, and administrative aspects carried out in 6 work packages. The primary outcomes of the PPP are the setting-up of the legal and financial frameworks of the functioning of the RI; the preparation of signature-ready documents towards the implementation phase; the completion of the RESILIENCE service catalogue, and the establishment of legal agreements and technical frameworks for their operation.

RESILIENCE (Religious Studies Infrastructure: toolS, Innovation, Experts, conNectiOns and Centres in Europe) is a distributed Research Infrastructure that entered the ESFRI Roadmap in 2021. Its mission is to address the challenge of creating a larger, structured involvement of excellent scholars who innovatively produce competencies, knowledge, approaches, and impact within the scientific domain of Religious Studies.

The RESILIENCE PPP consortium is composed by

- FONDAZIONE PER LE SCIENZE RELIGIOSE GIOVANNI XXIII (FSCIRE), the Coordinator
- BAR ILAN UNIVERSITY (BIU)
- CINECA CONSORZIO INTERUNIVERSITARIO (CINECA)
- ECOLE PRATIQUE DES HAUTES ETUDES (EPHE)
- INSTITUT FÜR ANGEWANDTE INFORMATIK (INFAI)
- KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT LEUVEN (KU Leuven)
- SOFIA UNIVERSITY ST KLIMENT OHRIDSKI (UNISOFIA)
- THEOLOGISCHE UNIVERSITEIT APELDOORN (TUA),
- ALBANIAN UNIVERSITY (UFO)
- UNIVERZITET U SARAJEVU (UNSA)
- UNIWERSYTET WARSZAWSKI (UNIWARSAW)
- VOLOS ACADEMY FOR THEOLOGICAL STUDIES (VOLOS)
- WESTFAELISCHE WILHELMS-UNIVERSITAET MUENSTER (WWU)

This document is the Detailed Organisation Plan (DOP) for the Grant and represents the reference document by which RESILIENCE demonstrates that it:

- understands the WP, its characteristics, peculiarities, risks, innovations, and unknowns,
- has selected the most appropriate WP organisations, techniques, resources, and tools to cope with the above,
- has defined the deliverables, quality assurance, and approval responsibilities and processes and defined the extent and format of checks and reviews,
- has identified the major risks and the corresponding preventive actions.

The major purposes of this DOP are:

- To define the organisational structures that govern the RESILIENCE PPP;
- Describe the processes, instruments necessary for the proper governance of the RESILIENCE PPP;
- To assure REA about the respect of the GA procedures;
- To define roles and responsibilities, with emphasis on the required skill sets, to address the complexities and risks of the RESILIENCE PPP,
- To make visible all the means that are applied at governance level to meet the GA requirements,
- To ensure that the GA governance requirements are fully understood by RESILIENCE PPP,
- To state all the participants of the WP, procedures, rules, and applicable methods.

1.2. Scope

This DOP covers exclusively the GA organisational bodies of RESILIENCE PPP as defined in the Grant Agreement number 101079792.

This DOP is to be applied by each staff employed on the RESILIENCE PPP and to all work performed within it. It is a binding document being part of the contractual documents. In case of misinterpretation or conflicts, the Grant Agreement Contract and its annexes have precedence over this document.

2. Presentation of the Grant Agreement

2.1. Definition of the objectives of RESILIENCE PPP

RESILIENCE is a new ESFRI research infrastructure (RI) project identified in the 2021 update of the ESFRI Roadmap. Its mission is to address the challenge of creating a larger, structured involvement of excellent scholars who innovatively produce competencies, knowledge, approaches and impact within the scientific domain of Religious Studies.

In the long term, the RI aims at:

- a) increasing and systematising inter- and multidisciplinary activities to create larger scientific aggregations capable of facilitating further exchanges between the various super-specialised and overarching research approaches to religion;
- b) assembling results and paving the way for more effective research (investing money to produce knowledge) and more innovation (investing knowledge to produce money);
- c) offering access to a platform supplying data, tools and expertise for the Religious Studies community;
- d) supplying data, tools and expertise for the Religious Studies community;
- e) supporting scholars in bringing knowledge about religion back to the academic and public debate, on topics such as religious rights and freedoms, violence, contrasting hermeneutics;
- f) making expertise and knowledge on Religious Studies accessible to public actors.

Through the RI, the scholarly community will take advantage of broader and more structured involvement in a platform of highly qualified scholars and with community-tailored technology.

In accordance with the long term aims of the RI and the work programme topic, the main objective of the proposed work is to bring the RESILIENCE RI to the completion of its Preparatory Phase (PP), which started in 2021 and will end in 2025. Such completion is reached through the following steps¹:

- 1) Start of the procedure to establish ERIC legal structure
- 2) Definition of the financial support and strategy
- 3) Signing of formal agreements with service providers and TNA facilities not included in the consortium, including other RIs
- 4) Scientific vision & mission finalised
- 5) User strategy finalised and system for continuous check on user needs defined
- 6) Access policy detailed, TNA call-cycle ready to implement
- 7) Definition of standards and FAIR data policy
- 8) Data Management service strategy ready to enter the Implementation Phase
- 9) Technical Implementation Model for development, integrating, building, testing, deploying and operating software
- 10) Service Catalogue strategy and model completed, with first set of services added

2.2. Global contract phasing

The REA imposes a certain phasing related to the reporting obligations of the RESILIENCE PPP partners. These are:

- Continuous reporting M1 to M48
- Reporting periods
 - M1 to M12 (5/2023)
 - M13 to M30 (11/2024)
- Final Reporting at M48 (5/2026)

Figure 1 : Reporting obligations

To execute and respect the Reporting procedures created by REA, RESILIENCE PPP partners rely on the following material:

- The GA;

¹ Please note that following the development of the RESILIENCE PPP, this list presents a more refined version of the objectives enlisted in the project proposal.

- A Consortium agreement based on the DESCA – Model Consortium Agreement for Horizon Europe, version 1, December 2021;
- Templates for financial reporting (those regarding technical reporting in Horizon EU projects have not been published to date. Cf. D6.2 Templates and guidelines for the monitoring, reporting and management activities, available on the RESILIENCE website);
- The grant management system offered through the European Commission Research&Innovation webportal Grant Organization.

3. Organization, Roles and Responsibilities

3.1.1. REA

The contact person for the RESILIENCE PPP is Emiliano Carozza, Project Advisor of the REA, Unit C.4 Reforming European R&I and Research Infrastructures. His email address is emiliano.carozza@ec.europa.eu

3.1.2. RESILIENCE PPP

RESILIENCE PPP governance, roles, responsibilities and staffing are extensively described in

- D8.1 RESILIENCE Governance, HR Policy and management and Access Policy (RESILIENCE 2YSEP GA n. 871127)
- Consortium agreement based on the DESCA – Model Consortium Agreement for Horizon Europe, version 1, December 2021
- D6.1 Governance set-up proceedings (RESILIENCE PPP GA n. 101079792), which is a public document available on the RESILIENCE website.

3.1.3. Work Packages (WPs) organisation

The work of RESILIENCE PPP is structured in 6 distinct Work Packages (WP). These are:

As it is mentioned in D6.1 Governance set-up proceedings, “With the purpose of matching the RESILIENCE PPP with the governance envisioned in the above-mentioned D8.1, RESILIENCE Governance, HR Policy and Management and Access Policy, Directors revised some structural aspects (i.e., Units are now called Working Units (WU); RESILIENCE PPP Work Package (WP) 5 on Impact is absorbed in WP3 as a dedicated WU) and agreed on the following structure:”

WP	Work Package	Working Unit	Lead Beneficiary	Start Month	End Month
WP1	Sustainability	HR and Other Resources	FSCIRE	1	42
		Funding			
WP2	Services	Data	KU Leuven	2	47
		IT			
		TNA			
WP3	Users	User Requirements	WWU	2	43
		Impact (WP5)	UNSA	2	48

WP4	Communication	Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation	TUA	2	48
		Training			
WP6	Project Management		FSCIRE	2	48

Table 1 : List of Work Packages and Work Units

According to the way the work is distributed within the WPs, along with the WP leader and WU leader, there are also task leaders and task team members.

3.1.3.1. WP Leader

For a WP, the team leader is responsible for the coordination of the team ensuring the WP development and related deliverables formally requested within the GA. In coordination with the Project Coordinator (PC), the WP leader participates to the WP management and defines a Work Breakdown Structure, proposes the realisation agenda, and leads the WP realisation.

The responsibilities of the WP Leader are, apart from performing general project management, to perform quality assessment of the deliverables before their submission for acceptance to the Board of Directors and then to the REA.

WP Leader’s responsibilities include:

- informing the PC about WP status including work progress, risks, utilization of resources, Key Performance Indicators, etc.
- examining and discussing with the WU leaders and institutions responsible for the Task delivery all matters related to individual tasks in development and their connections with other tasks, WUs and WPs,
- performing quality audits related to Best Practice usage and quality conformity related to the Quality Assessment Plan,
- reading and verifying content-related conformity of received deliverables against GA assumptions,
- verifying the correction of deliverables’ issues discovered by reviews performed by BoD and/or REA before formally (re)submitting the deliverable for acceptance to BoD and/or REA,
- informing the WU leaders and institutions responsible for the Task delivery about development of new topics or changes in the existing WP deliverables.
- Being the point of contact of the PC for all issues related to the specific WP

One or more members of the WP team assist in generating the draft and final version of the deliverables.

4. GA execution

The execution of the Grant Agreement is ensured by a Work Breakdown Structure which organises all the effort, tasks, milestones, and deliverables of the project, according to the timing approved by the REA. You can find the WBS below, divided into WPs.

4.1. WP Effort

Participant	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	Total Person-Months
1 - FSCIRE	37.80	43.60	1.00	1.60		29.70	113.70
2 - BIU		4.30		0.10		1.30	5.70
3 - CINECA		27.60	0.40	2.10		1.30	31.40
4 - EPHE		3.10		0.10		1.30	4.50
5 - INFAI	7.70	27.80	11.30	0.10		1.30	48.20
6 - KU Leuven	1.10	41.20	4.00	0.10		1.50	47.90
7 - UNISOFIA	5.70	5.10	3.60	5.00	1.70	1.30	22.40
8 - TUA	9.80	7.60	0.70	24.40	1.70	11.30	55.50
9 - UFO	4.60	18.70	0.40	2.30		1.30	27.30
10 - UNSA		4.30	3.60	2.30	10.80	1.30	22.30
11 - UNIWARSAW	4.60	7.40	1.80	0.10	1.70	1.30	16.90
12 - VOLOS		3.10		0.80		1.30	5.20
13 - WWU	5.70	6.50	42.60	1.90		1.30	58.00
Total Person-Months	77.00	200.30	69.40	40.90	15.90	55.50	459.00

Figure 2: Overview of the effort per WP and RESILIENCE PPP partner

4.2. WP Planning

4.2.1. WP1

Work Package	GA Task ID	Task	Milestone ID	Deliverable ID	Total Effort
WP1	Task1.1.0	Establishment of the ERIC			
WP1	Task1.1.1	Other Research Infrastructure			
WP1	Task1.1.2	Meetings (#20)			60d
WP1	Task1.1.3	Experience and lessons learned – Collection and compilation			25d
WP1	Task1.1.4	ERIC Requirements Definition			
WP1	Task1.1.5	Collective Workshops (#4)			32d
WP1	Task1.1.6	ERIC Statuses			
WP1	Task1.1.7	Advisory activities (with Advisor indicated by the Italian Ministry of Research)			40d

WP1	Task1.1.8	D1.1 RESILIENCE ERIC Statutes, bylaws, and protocols – Drafting			35d
WP1	Task1.1.9	Reviews and revision			150d
WP1	Task1.1.10	D1.1 Acceptance and publication	M1.1	D1.1	5d
WP1	Task1.1.11	D1.2 RESILIENCE ERIC Statutes, bylaws, and protocols – FINAL		D1.2	5d
WP1	Task1.1.12	Creation of the ERIC	M1.2		50d
WP1	Task1.2.0	Business model and Financial Plan for PP and IP			
WP1	Task1.2.1	Workshop on Resilience Business Model (#2)			10d
WP1	Task1.2.2	Drafting of D1.3 Financial Sustainability Plan			20d
WP1	Task1.2.3	Data collection for all typologies of costs			150d
WP1	Task1.2.4	Simulation for the revenues model			20d
WP1	Task1.2.5	Workshop with RESILIENCE stakeholders to present D1.3			10d
WP1	Task1.2.6	Workshop with external stakeholders to present D1.3			5d
WP1	Task1.2.7	D1.3 Financial Sustainability Plan			
WP1	Task1.2.8	Reviews and revision			5d
WP1	Task1.2.9	D1.3 Acceptance and publication	M1.3	D1.3	2d
WP1	Task1.3.0	Support to the applications for political and financial support			
WP1	Task1.3.1	National Research Infrastructures			
WP1	Task1.3.2	Meetings (#40, at least 5 meetings per partner)			35d
WP1	Task1.3.3	Debriefing and minutes			17,5d
WP1	Task1.3.4	Agreements set-up			45d
WP1	Task1.3.5	International Research Infrastructures			
WP1	Task1.3.6	Meetings (#20)			17,5d
WP1	Task1.3.7	Debriefing and minutes			17,5d
WP1	Task1.3.8	Agreements set-up			20d
WP1	Task1.3.9	Partnerships Management			
WP1	Task1.3.10	Meetings (#40)			35d
WP1	Task1.3.11	Debriefing and minutes			17,5d
WP1	Task1.3.12	Agreements set-up			35d
WP1	Task1.3.13	Co-creation of material, support for political and financial support			
WP1	Task1.3.14	Workshops (#5)			50d
WP1	Task1.3.15	Material creation			35d
WP1	Task1.3.16	Mutual support in national related activities			280d
WP1	Task1.3.17	Report of activities results to the GenA (#8)			
WP1	Task1.3.18	Drafting			56d
WP1	Task1.3.19	Reviews and revision			14d
WP1	Task1.3.20	Acceptance and publication			4d

4.2.2. WP2

Work Package	GA Task ID	Task	Milestone ID	Deliverable ID	Total Effort
WP2	Task2.1.0	Strategy of Services for PP and IP			
WP2	Task2.1.1	Analysis of synergies possibilities			
WP2	Task2.1.2	Meetings (#5)			30d
WP2	Task2.1.3	Information collection and analysis			80d
WP2	Task2.1.4	Drafting the D2.1 – Services Preparation and Implementation Strategy			10d
WP2	Task2.1.5	Risk Management			
WP2	Task2.1.6	Meetings (#5)			35d
WP2	Task2.1.7	Information collection and analysis			60d
WP2	Task2.1.8	Updating the D2.1			10d
WP2	Task2.1.9	Mission and Vision statement including methods, tools, standars			
WP2	Task2.1.10	Meetings (#5)			35d
WP2	Task2.1.11	Information collection and analysis			80d
WP2	Task2.1.12	Updating the D2.1			20d
WP2	Task2.1.13	Strategical and Operational planning			
WP2	Task2.1.14	Meetings (#5)			35d
WP2	Task2.1.15	Information collection and analysis			80d
WP2	Task2.1.16	Updating the D2.1			20d
WP2	Task2.1.17	D2.1 – Services Preparation and Implementation Strategy			
WP2	Task2.1.18	Updates to the deliverable			40d
WP2	Task2.1.19	Services Strategy Modelling (ie Archimate)			50d
WP2	Task2.1.20	Final revision			25d
WP2	Task2.1.21	D2.1 Acceptance and publication	M2.1	D2.1	2d
WP2	Task2.2.0	Preparing User Services for PP and IP			
WP2	Task2.2.1	Service Catalogue creation			
WP2	Task2.2.2	Preparation Workshops (#4)			68d
WP2	Task2.2.3	User Services Analysis			135d
WP2	Task2.2.4	User Services Modelling (ie Archimate)			117,5d
WP2	Task2.2.5	Review Workshops (#4)			44d
WP2	Task2.2.6	Drafting of D2.2			25d
WP2	Task2.2.7	Analysis of costs and resources available			
WP2	Task2.2.8	Review Workshops (#2)			50d
WP2	Task2.2.9	Selection and prioritisation of users services to be implemented			
WP2	Task2.2.10	Review Workshops (#2)			32,5d
WP2	Task2.2.11	D2.2 – User Services Catalogue			
WP2	Task2.2.12	Reviews and revision			37d
WP2	Task2.2.13	D2.2 Acceptance and publication	M2.2	D2.2	4d
WP2	Task2.3.0	Preparing IT Services			
WP2	Task2.3.1	IT Service Catalogue creation			
WP2	Task2.3.2	Preparation Workshops (#4)			33d
WP2	Task2.3.3	IT Services Analysis			63d
WP2	Task2.3.4	IT Services Modelling (ie Archimate)			113d
WP2	Task2.3.5	Review Workshops (#4)			21d

WP2	Task2.3.6	Drafting of D2.3			10d
WP2	Task2.3.7	Analysis of technical feasibility, costs and resources estimation			
WP2	Task2.3.8	Defining evaluation method and criteria			11d
WP2	Task2.3.9	Evaluating existing SW and services (#10 labs)			90d
WP2	Task2.3.10	Review Workshops (#10)			60d
WP2	Task2.3.11	Selection and prioritisation of IT services to be implemented			
WP2	Task2.3.12	Review Workshops (#2)			12,5d
WP2	Task2.3.13	D2.7 – Security Management Plan (SMP)		D2.7	
WP2	Task2.3.14	D2.3 – IT Services Catalogue			
WP2	Task2.3.15	Reviews and revision			18d
WP2	Task2.3.16	D2.3 Acceptance and publication	M2.3	D2.3	2d
WP2	Task2.3.17	D2.8 – Software Development Plan Template (SDPT)		D2.8	
WP2	Task2.3.18	Preparation of Data Centre Services			
WP2	Task2.3.19	D2.9 – Data centre Services Mgt Plan		D2.9	
WP2	Task2.3.20	Technical analysis			95d
WP2	Task2.3.21	Planning and resource allocation			40d
WP2	Task2.3.22	Documentation			150d
WP2	Task2.3.23	Implementation			390d
WP2	Task2.3.24	Test			235d
WP2	Task2.3.25	D2.10 – Operation Management Policy (OMP)		D2.10	
WP2	Task2.3.26	Operational set-up			80d
WP2	Task2.3.27	Support			35d
WP2	Task2.4.0	Data Management Services			
WP2	Task2.4.1	Data Services Brainstorming			
WP2	Task2.4.2	Preparation Workshops (#4)			26d
WP2	Task2.4.3	Data Management Services Analysis			45d
WP2	Task2.4.4	Services Modelling (ie Archimate)			25d
WP2	Task2.4.5	Review Workshops (#4)			24d
WP2	Task2.4.6	Input to D2.2 and D2.3			10d
WP2	Task2.4.7	Analysis of costs and resources available			
WP2	Task2.4.8	Review Workshops (#2)			12d
WP2	Task2.4.9	Selection and prioritisation of services to be implemented			
WP2	Task2.4.10	Review Workshops (#2)			12d
WP2	Task2.4.11	D2.11 master/Reference Data Management Plan (MDM)	M2.4	D2.11	10d
WP2	Task2.5.0	Data Management Plan			
WP2	Task2.5.1	Preparation of Data Management Plan			
WP2	Task2.5.2	Collecting input on data produced and collected by the project			4d
WP2	Task2.5.3	Virtual information sessions on proper data handling, incl. GDPR (#3)			9d
WP2	Task2.5.4	Drafting D2.4 Data management plan			5d

WP2	Task2.5.5	Reviewing data handling and organisation, incl. quality control of partner uploads and improvements			7d
WP2	Task2.5.6	Long term archiving and publication of core Resilience data according to FAIR principles. Includes ingest jobs, access settings, persistent identification, data publication			4d
WP2	Task2.5.7	Researching the practical implementation of FAIR data practices in the e-infra landscape			7d
WP2	Task2.5.8	Researching the current state and challenges of FAIR data sharing in Religious studies			7d
WP2	Task2.5.9	Drafting a strategy for the increased understanding and uptake of FAIR data sharing in religious studies			5d
WP2	Task2.5.10	Presentation and Q&A to all partners on what FAIR means for religious studies (#1)			14d
WP2	Task2.5.11	Strategy on data collecting, production and processing of the Resilience RI			7d
WP2	Task2.5.12	Updating D2.4			4d
WP2	Task2.5.13	D2.4 Data Management Plan			
WP2	Task2.5.14	Reviews and revision			3d
WP2	Task2.5.15	D.2.4 Acceptance and publication	M2.5	D.2.4	2d
WP2	Task2.6.0	Preparing TNA activities			
WP2	Task2.6.1	TNA Services Brainstorming			
WP2	Task2.6.2	Preparation Workshops (#4)			32d
WP2	Task2.6.3	TNA Services Analysis			25d
WP2	Task2.6.4	Services Modelling (ie Archimate)			50d
WP2	Task2.6.5	Review Workshops (#4)			31d
WP2	Task2.6.6	Input to D2.5			15d
WP2	Task2.6.7	Analysis of costs and resources available			
WP2	Task2.6.8	Review Workshops (#2)			16d
WP2	Task2.6.9	Selection and prioritisation of services to be implemented			
WP2	Task2.6.10	Review Workshops (#2)			28d
WP2	Task2.6.11	Testing the TNA Services Management Plan			
WP2	Task2.6.12	Prototyping services	M2.6		390d
WP2	Task2.6.13	Feedback collection			50d
WP2	Task2.6.14	D2.12 TNA – Management Report (TNA-MR)		D2.12	15d
WP2	Task2.6.15	D2.5 – TNA Services Management Plan			
WP2	Task2.6.16	Updates to the deliverable			15d
WP2	Task2.6.17	Final revision			10d
WP2	Task2.6.18	D2.5 Acceptance and publication	M2.7	D2.5	6d
WP2	Task2.7.0	Preparing Training Services activities			
WP2	Task2.7.1	Training Services Brainstorming			
WP2	Task2.7.2	Preparation Workshops (#4)			32d
WP2	Task2.7.3	Training Services Analysis			25d
WP2	Task2.7.4	Services Modelling (ie Archimate)			60d
WP2	Task2.7.5	Review Workshops (#4)			25d
WP2	Task2.7.6	Input to D2.6			17d

WP2	Task2.7.7	Analysis of costs and resources available			
WP2	Task2.7.8	Review Workshops (#2)			16d
WP2	Task2.7.9	Selection and prioritisation of services to be implemented			
WP2	Task2.7.10	Review Workshops (#2)			16d
WP2	Task2.7.11	Testing the Training Services Management Plan			
WP2	Task2.7.12	Prototyping services	M2.8		390d
WP2	Task2.7.13	Feedback collection			35d
WP2	Task2.7.14	D2.13 Trainings – Management Report (T-MR)		D2.13	27d
WP2	Task2.7.15	D2.6 – Training Services Management Plan			
WP2	Task2.7.16	Updates to the deliverable			17d
WP2	Task2.7.17	Final revision			9d
WP2	Task2.7.18	D2.6 Acceptance and publication	M2.9	D2.6	4d

4.2.3. WP3

Work Package	GA Task ID	Task	Milestone ID	Deliverable ID	Total Effort
WP3	Task3.1.0	User Requirements			
WP3	Task3.1.1	Definition of an approach for collecting detailed User Requirements			
WP3	Task3.1.2	Information collection and analysis			20d
WP3	Task3.1.3	Meetings (#2)			17d
WP3	Task3.1.4	Approach definition and creation of input for the D2.2 and D2.3			10d
WP3	Task3.1.5	User Requirements – Data collection			
WP3	Task3.1.6	Workshops with 10-20 Users (#5)			57d
WP3	Task3.1.7	Information collection and analysis			63d
WP3	Task3.1.8	Creation of D3.1			15d
WP3	Task3.1.9	Focus Groups			
WP3	Task3.1.10	Focus Group workshops with 20 users (#10)			38d
WP3	Task3.1.11	Collecting the feedback from the Focus Groups			22d
WP3	Task3.1.12	Updating D3.1			10d
WP3	Task3.1.13	D3.1 – Workshop Proceedings – 1 st Batch		D3.1	
WP3	Task3.1.14	Updates to the deliverable			10d
WP3	Task3.1.15	Final revision			12d
WP3	Task3.1.16	D3.2 – Workshop Proceedings – 2 nd Batch			
WP3	Task3.1.17	D3.2 Acceptance and publication	M3.1	D3.2	2d
WP3	Task3.2.0	Use Cases			
WP3	Task3.2.1	Definition of Use Cases definition approach			
WP3	Task3.2.2	Preparation Workshops (#2)			42d
WP3	Task3.2.3	Describe the approach into D3.3			10d
WP3	Task3.2.4	Use Cases creation			
WP3	Task3.2.5	Workshops with 10-20 Users (#5)			52d
WP3	Task3.2.6	Use Cases Analysis			52d
WP3	Task3.2.7	Use Cases Modelling (ie Modelio)			117d
WP3	Task3.2.8	D3.3 – Use Cases Catalogue – 1 st batch		D3.3	

WP3	Task3.2.9	D3.3 – Reviews and revision			19d
WP3	Task3.2.10	Collective analysis and review of the Use Cases			75d
WP3	Task3.2.11	Use Cases – Review Workshops (#10)			75d
WP3	Task3.2.12	Synchronising the Use Cases with WP2 team(s)			25d
WP3	Task3.2.13	Updating D3.3			20d
WP3	Task3.2.14	D3.4 – Use Cases Catalogue – 2 nd batch			
WP3	Task3.2.15	D3.4 Acceptance and publication	M3.2	D3.4	2d
WP3	Task3.2.16	UX/UI mock-ups			
WP3	Task3.2.17	Definition of the approach (method, tools, etc.) to create the mock-ups			15d
WP3	Task3.2.18	Mock-ups creation (#100)			250d
WP3	Task3.2.19	Synchronising the mock-ups with WP2 team(s)			25d
WP3	Task3.2.20	Finalisation of the mock-ups			10d
WP3	Task3.2.21	Identify potential UX/UI elements that could be part of UX/UI RESILIENCE charter			25d
WP3	Task3.3.0	User Stories			
WP3	Task3.3.1	Definition of Use Stories definition approach			
WP3	Task3.3.2	Preparation Workshops (#2)			42d
WP3	Task3.3.3	Describe the approach into D3.5			10d
WP3	Task3.3.4	User Stories creation			
WP3	Task3.3.5	Workshops with 10-20 Users (#5)			52d
WP3	Task3.3.6	User Stories Analysis			92d
WP3	Task3.3.7	D3.5 – User Stories Catalogue – 1 st Batch		D3.5	
WP3	Task3.3.8	D3.5 – Reviews and revision			22d
WP3	Task3.3.9	Updating D3.5			25d
WP3	Task3.3.10	Creation of AAI service input for D2.2 and D2.3			25d
WP3	Task3.3.11	Synchronising the mock-ups with WP2 team(s)			25d
WP3	Task3.3.12	D3.6 – User Stories Catalogue – 2 nd Batch			
WP3	Task3.3.13	D3.6 Acceptance and publication	M3.3	D3.6	2d

4.2.4. WP4

Work Package	GA Task ID	Task	Milestone ID	Deliverable ID	Total Effort
WP4	Task4.1.0	Communication and Dissemination (CD) Strategy – Implementation			
WP4	Task4.1.1	CD Strategy – Definition			
WP4	Task4.1.2	Brainstorming workshops (#3) to define goals, strategy, functionalities of c&d tools			25d
WP4	Task4.1.3	Drafting D4.1			15d
WP4	Task4.1.4	Presentation of D4.1			13,5d
WP4	Task4.1.5	D4.1 – Communication and Dissemination Plan – 1 st Release			
WP4	Task4.1.6	Reviews and revision			8,5d
WP4	Task4.1.7	D4.1 Acceptance and publication	M4.1	D4.1	2d
WP4	Task4.1.8	CD Strategy – Implementation			

WP4	Task4.1.9	Requirements for the CD monitoring and analytics tooling			19d
WP4	Task4.1.10	Creation of Input for monitoring and analytics for D4.2 and D4.3			17d
WP4	Task4.1.11	Implementation/operation of monitoring and analytics tooling			60d
WP4	Task4.1.12	Translation of press releases and other dissemination material into minority languages			15,5d
WP4	Task4.1.13	Ongoing collection of material for communication and dissemination channels			61d
WP4	Task4.1.14	Presence on external events			140d
WP4	Task4.1.15	Organisation of RESILIENCE events			100d
WP4	Task4.1.16	PP website Maintenance			50d
WP4	Task4.1.17	PP Newsletters (#25, #5 done per partner and managed by TUA)			25d
WP4	Task4.1.18	PP Social Network activities (Twitter, LinkedIN, YouTube, Instagram)			85d
WP4	Task4.1.19	Updating D4.1			20d
WP4	Task4.1.20	D4.2 – Communication and Dissemination Plan – 2 nd Release			
WP4	Task4.1.21	Reviews and revisions			11d
WP4	Task4.1.22	Acceptance and publication		D4.2	2d
WP4	Task4.1.23	Monitoring of analytics			53d
WP4	Task4.1.24	Updating D4.2 (and eventual impacts on D4.1)			20d
WP4	Task4.1.25	D4.3 – Communication and Dissemination Plan – 3 rd Release – Looking Forward			
WP4	Task4.1.26	Reviews and revision			8,5d
WP4	Task4.1.27	D4.3 Acceptance and publication		D4.3	2d
WP4	Task4.2.0	Study on a subset of SERVICES			
WP4	Task4.2.1	Identification of the services to be studied			
WP4	Task4.2.2	Preparation Workshop			6d
WP4	Task4.2.3	Describe the selection and selection criteria into D4.2			5d
WP4	Task4.2.4	Services communication study			
WP4	Task4.2.5	Workshops with 10-20 Users (#3)			19d
WP4	Task4.2.6	Communication Analysis (typology, strategy, performance, etc.)			20d
WP4	Task4.2.7	Analysis and review of the discoveries			14d
WP4	Task4.2.8	Results presentation workshop			8d
WP4	Task4.2.9	Drafting D4.4			5d
WP4	Task4.2.10	D4.4 – Study the communication for a subset of services			
WP4	Task4.2.11	Reviews and revision			8d
WP4	Task4.2.12	D4.4 Acceptance and publication		D4.4	2d

4.2.5. WP5

Work Package	GA Task ID	Task	Milestone ID	Deliverable ID	Total Effort
WP5	Task5.1.0	Impact analysis			
WP5	Task5.1.1	Impact analysis Strategy – Definition			
WP5	Task5.1.2	Collective workshops (#3) to define goals, strategy, functionalities of c&d tools			19d
WP5	Task5.1.3	Drafting D5.1			20d
WP5	Task5.1.4	Presentation of the impact analysis strategy drafted in D5.1			6d
WP5	Task5.1.5	Impact Analysis – Implementation			
WP5	Task5.1.6	Participation to the other WP activities to collect impact information			175d
WP5	Task5.1.7	Analysis of the data collected			50d
WP5	Task5.1.8	Workshop organisation to confirm discoveries			6d
WP5	Task5.1.9	Results presentation workshop			6d
WP5	Task5.1.10	Updating D5.1 (and eventual impacts on other WPs)			15d
WP5	Task5.1.11	D5.1 – Impact Analysis report			
WP5	Task5.1.12	Reviews and revision			19d
WP5	Task5.1.13	D5.1 Acceptance and publication	M5.1	D5.1	2d

4.2.6. WP6

Work Package	GA Task ID	Task	Milestone ID	Deliverable ID	Total Effort
WP6	Task6.1.0	Implementing RESILIENCE governance structure			
WP6	Task6.1.1	Kick-off (preparation, running, minutes) START 1/6/2022	M6.1		29d
WP6	Task6.1.2	Board of Directors – IN KIND (4 FTE/Year)			
WP6	Task6.1.3	Governance structure – Running			
WP6	Task6.1.4	General Assembly (GenA) + Board of Directors (BoD) meetings (#4)			104d
WP6	Task6.1.5	GenA + BoD meeting minutes			4d
WP6	Task6.1.6	BoD + Service Coordination Committee (SCC) monthly meetings (#48)			96d
WP6	Task6.1.7	BoD + SCC meeting minutes			24d
WP6	Task6.1.8	BOD + Advisory Board (AB)+ SCC meetings(#8)			32d
WP6	Task6.1.9	BoD + AB + SCC meeting minutes			4d
WP6	Task6.1.10	D6.1 Governance set-up proceedings		D6.1	
WP6	Task6.1.11	Grant Agreement/Consortium Agreement – Back Office			160d
WP6	Task6.1.12	Grant Management – Financial Aspects			40d
WP6	Task6.1.13	Project Management Tools and Infrastructure			80d
WP6	Task6.1.14	PP phase closure			
WP6	Task6.1.15	Closure event (in Bologna/Palermo)	M6.4		32d
WP6	Task6.2.0	Project Management Tools and Infrastructure			

WP6	Task6.2.1	D6.3 Detailed Organisational Plan (DOP)			
WP6	Task6.2.2	Preparation			20d
WP6	Task6.2.3	Reviews and revision			5d
WP6	Task6.2.4	D6.3 Acceptance and publication	M6.2	D6.3	2d
WP6	Task6.2.5	D6.4 Quality Assurance Plan (QAP)		D6.4	
WP6	Task6.2.6	RESILIENCE internal trainings			
WP6	Task6.2.7	Training sessions for all (#6 incl. Organisation design, Agile Mgt, UX/UI, etc.)			168d
WP6	Task6.2.8	Quality Assurance of the RESILIENCE activities			
WP6	Task6.2.9	Workshop to discuss RESILIENCE Quality Assurance requirements			17d
WP6	Task6.2.10	D6.2 Templates and guidelines for monitoring, reporting and management activities			
WP6	Task6.2.11	Preparation			20d
WP6	Task6.2.12	Reviews and revision			5d
WP6	Task6.2.13	D6.2 Acceptance and publication	M6.3	D6.2	2d
WP6	Task6.2.14	Quality Assurance Monitoring activities			100d
WP6	Task6.2.15	Continuous improvement			100d
WP6	Task6.3.0	Data Management			
WP6	Task6.3.1	D2.4 Data Management Plan – Update of T2.5 activities			
WP6	Task6.3.2	Reviews and revision			4d

4.3. Deliverables of the RESILIENCE PPP

The work conducted by the RESILIENCE PPP is made accessible and testified by 31 deliverables, described as follows:

WP No	Deliv. Related No	Deliv. No	Deliverable Name	Description	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemin. Level	Due Date
WP1	D1.1	D1	RESILIENCE ERIC Statutes, bylaws and protocols – 1 st draft	The deliverable collects all documents requested for the establishment of the ERIC in their first version	FSCIRE	R	PU	30 Nov 2024
WP1	D1.2	D2	RESILIENCE ERIC Statutes bylaws and protocols – last version	The deliverable collects all documents requested for the establishment of the ERIC in their latest version before the signature of the Member Countries.	FSCIRE	R	PU	30 Nov 2025
WP1	D1.3	D3	Financial Sustainability Plan	The deliverable presents the Business Model and Financial Plan for the later stages of the Preparatory Phase and the Implementation Phase, and the transition from one to the other.	FSCIRE	R	PU	31 May 2024
WP2	D2.1	D4	Services Preparation and Implementation Strategy	Detailed description of the strategy for implementing RESILIENCE services	FSCIRE	R	PU	31 Jul 2025

WP No	Deliv. Related No	Deliv. No	Deliverable Name	Description	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemin. Level	Due Date
WP2	D2.2	D5	User Services Catalogue	Organised, curated and documented collection of any and all user services that can be performed on the RESILIENCE platform.	KU Leuven	R	PU	30 Nov 2025
WP2	D2.3	D6	IT Services Catalogue	Organised, curated and documented collection of any and all IT services supporting the user services operated on the RESILIENCE platform.	FSCIRE	R	PU	30 Apr 2026
WP2	D2.4	D7	Data Management Plan	Plan detailing how to make data FAIR, including what data RESILIENCE manages, whether and how it is made accessible for verification and re-use, and how it will be curated and preserved.	KU Leuven	DMP	PU	30 Sep 2025
WP2	D2.5	D8	TNA Services Management Plan	The TNA Management Plan describes criteria of excellence for TNA hosts and users, their rights and duties within the program, quality monitoring procedures and responsibilities (incl. Peer Review Committee), and efficient information providing and research enhancing workflows.	KU Leuven	R	PU	31 Oct 2025
WP2	D2.6	D9	Training Services Management Plan	The Training Management Plan defines the model of training activities provided by RESILIENCE and represents a guide for the partners involved in training activities.	TUA	R	PU	31 Jul 2025
WP2	D2.7	D13	Security Management Plan (SMP)	The Security Management Plan is elaborated to define all aspects of the working practices of the project to guarantee secure delivery. It contains a Secure Coding/Development Guidelines aligned with "ISO/IEC 27034 Information technology – Security techniques", the OWASP Developer Guide, Testing Guide and Top-10 Application Security Risks	FSCIRE	R	PU	30 Nov 2023
WP2	D2.8	D14	Software Development Plan Template (SDPT)	The Software Development Plan Template is elaborated to define all best practices for the development, testing and installation of a software to be created and maintained within the context of RESILIENCE. The SDPT is foundational for the IT aspect of RESILIENCE, since each software project will then create an instance of this template specifically adapted to the software maintained	KU Leuven	R	PU	30 Nov 2023

WP No	Deliv. Related No	Deliv. No	Deliverable Name	Description	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemin. Level	Due Date
WP2	D2.9	D15	Data Centre Services – Services Level Requirements (SLR)	Collection of the project services requirements from all management team members. This information, a mandatory ITIL deliverable will be presented as Service Level Requirements (SLR) and is an important deliverable that must be clearly defined, documented, signed off, and understood by all project stakeholders before the Data Centre Services service could be delivered.	FSCIRE	R	PU	31 May 2024
WP2	D2.10	D16	Operation Management Policy (OMP)	From the DCS-SLR, the team will create an Operations Management Policy that will contain operation guidelines and responsibilities, service level arrangements and delivery conditions.	KU Leuven	R	PU	31 May 2025
WP2	D2.11	D17	Master/Reference Data Management (MDM)	For all services to be aligned with researchers’ needs in terms of data exchange, RESILIENCE needs to establish a Reference Data Architecture as well as the processes to maintain it during the whole RI duration. Our deliverable will be developed upon 2 levels of abstraction: - Data Level: Aligned with Master Data management, a common RESILIENCE Data dictionary is developed that covers all Religious Studies Research information systems. This allows all WPs applications to exchange information transparently. - Service Level: One step above, at service level, a common definition language is created in order to interoperate between systems with common semantic and structured language rules.	KU Leuven	R	PU	31 May 2025
WP2	D2.12	D18	TNA – Management Report (TNA-MR)	This deliverable will present the results of the pilot TNA activities, evaluating the results, difficulties and potential risks and opportunities.	KU Leuven	R	PU	30 Apr 2026
WP2	D2.13	D19	Trainings – Management Report (T-MR)	This deliverable presents the results of the pilot training activities, evaluating the results, difficulties and potential risks and opportunities.	TUA	R	PU	30 Apr 2026
WP3	D3.1	D10	Workshops proceedings – 1 st batch	Collection of notes and media documents presenting the highlights of all Design Thinking workshops.	WWU	R	PU	29 Feb 2024

WP No	Deliv. Related No	Deliv. No	Deliverable Name	Description	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemin. Level	Due Date
WP3	D3.2	D20	Workshop Proceedings – 2 nd batch	Collection of notes and media documents presenting the highlights of all Design Thinking workshops.	WWU	R	PU	30 Nov 2025
WP3	D3.3	D21	Documented Use Cases – 1 st batch	for each service, user/functional requirements are documented using use cases and collected within D3.1, including a set of S.M.A.R.T. objectives for the next project phase.	WWU	R	PU	31 Mar 2024
WP3	D3.4	D22	Documented Use Cases – 2 nd batch	For each service, user/functional requirements are documented using use cases and collected within D3.2, including a set of S.M.A.R.T. objectives for the next project phase	WWU	R	PU	30 Nov 2025
WP3	D3.5	D23	User Stories Catalogue – 1 st batch	Collections of User Stories allowing to identify roles connected with services functions	WWU	R	PU	31 Oct 2023
WP3	D3.6	D24	User Stories Catalogue – 2 nd batch	Collections of User Stories allowing to identify roles connected with services functions	WWU	R	PU	30 Nov 2024
WP4	D4.1	D11	Communication&Dissemination Plan – RESILIENCE PPP	The plan adapts C&D strategies to the developing structure of RESILIENCE, ensuring a sound coordination on what, how, when and to whom is communicated by the partners, and to be ready for the Implementation Phase	TUA	R	PU	31 Oct 2022
WP4	D4.2	D25	Communication and Dissemination Plan – RESILIENCE PPP, 2 nd version	The plan updates C&D strategies identified in D4.1 to the developing structure of RESILIENCE, ensuring a sound coordination on what, how, when and to whom is communicated by the partners, and to make a first balance of the strategy chosen and applied.	TUA	R	PU	30 Nov 2024
WP4	D4.3	D26	Communication and Dissemination Plan – RESILIENCE PPP, Looking forward	The plan updates C&D strategies identified in D4.1 to the developing structure of RESILIENCE, ensuring a sound coordination on what, how, when and to whom is communicated by the partners, and be ready for the Implementation Phase	TUA	R	PU	31 Jan 2026
WP4	D4.4	D27	Report on Study of the subset of services	The report details the input, activities, output and outcomes of the study conducted.	UNISOFIA	R	PU	31 Aug 2023
WP5	D5.1	D12	Impact analysis	The document reports on the measures of the RESILIENCE impact, the methodology chosen to identify and measure them according to the RESILIENCE impact areas and on the geographic areas where RESILIENCE hubs and nodes are present.	UNSA	R	PU	30 Nov 2025

WP No	Deliv. Related No	Deliv. No	Deliverable Name	Description	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemin. Level	Due Date
WP6	D6.1	D28	Governance set-up proceedings	GenA, BoD and WU members meet at the kick-off of the project, share and synchronise working rules. The calendar of meetings is adopted and made public.	FSCIRE	R	PU	30 Jun 2022
WP6	D6.2	D29	Templates and guidelines for the monitoring, reporting and management activities	Documents for financial, effort, and reporting monitoring are produced, shared among and explained to partners to support the project performance	FSCIRE	R	PU	31 Aug 2022
WP6	D6.3	D30	Detailed Organisational Plan (DOP)	The plan provides the tools for the management activities and also templates supporting the reporting activity.	FSCIRE	R	PU	31 Oct 2022
WP6	D6.4	D31	Quality Assessment Plan (QAP)	The plan details the Quality Management system adopted by RESILIENCE, including the processes for quality management and assessment, risks analysis, performance indicators management and a strategy to deal with ethics.	FSCIRE	R	PU	30 Sep 2022

4.4. WP management

At the global WP level, the report of the progress measurement is made to the Service Coordination Committee (SCC). The progress measurement and monitoring of the services are made – mainly – through the SCC Monthly meeting. The information on the work progress is communicated via the progress reports and via meeting minutes of the different committees.

4.5. Issue handling and escalation

The RESILIENCE PPP PC is responsible for collecting issues related to the execution of the GA. Each issue must be allocated to an owner and the issues will be followed up in the SCC Monthly Meeting or during ad hoc meetings. If no agreement is found during the SCC Monthly Meeting or the ad hoc meeting, and the GA and DESCA do not clearly address the case, the issue is escalated.

It is part of the responsibilities of each member of the WP to report and/or solve the problems. In case of conflict or critical problem (impact and priority), the escalation process is bottom-up from the author:

- 1) to the WU leader
- 2) to the WP leader
- 3) to the SCC
- 4) to the BoD
- 5) to the GenA
- 6) to the REA

Each level of escalation has to fix – after discussion and taking in consideration the GA and DESCA documents – the target date at which the issue must be answered and/or solved before escalation to the next higher level.

Escalation for urgent matters shall be done directly to each level responsible.

Escalation procedure shall be documented, reported, and followed up until closure.

4.6. Meetings

The different organisational bodies of the RESILIENCE PPP meet according to the timing and reasons presented in the following documents:

- D8.1 RESILIENCE Governance, HR Policy and management and Access Policy (RESILIENCE 2YSEP GA n. 871127)
- Consortium agreement based on the DESCA – Model Consortium Agreement for Horizon Europe, version 1, December 2021
- D6.1 Governance set-up proceedings (RESILIENCE PPP GA n. 101079792), which is a public document available on the RESILIENCE website.

Here you can find some additional details:

Type of meeting	Purpose	Convenor	Frequency	Report
GA meeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial, legal, enlargement strategy for the PP • Trend analysis • Description of the progress of the WP • Quality improvements 	PC/Chair	By-annual	Minutes
BoD meeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview of the status of the WP • Risk management • Activity progress • Open problems and proposed solutions • KPIs • Ad hoc initiatives 	Executive Director	Quarterly	Minutes
SCC Monthly meeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview of the status of the WP • Planning • Activity progress • Open problems and proposed solutions • Status of work orders • KPIs • Resource allocation 	PC	Monthly	Collaborative minutes: each participant is asked to contribute to a shared file made available on the dedicated task on the Clickup app

Type of meeting	Purpose	Convenor	Frequency	Report
Team meeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitoring the state of art of the activities/services • Open problems and proposal solutions • Sharing of information regarding current activities • Exchanges of information about any event regarding operational services and staffing (e.g. holidays, staff on leave, sickness) • Risks (security and others) 	WP Leader	According to WP needs	Minutes
Advisory Board meeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality evaluation of the work conducted • Advice on scientific development, strategy, finances, technical implementation 	PC/Chairperson of the body requesting the meeting	On demand	Minutes
Ad hoc Meeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Particular events • Reaction to critical problems • Escalation meeting 	PC	On demand	Minutes

Table 2: Meetings summary table

All minutes and meeting documents are located in the RESILIENCE PPP shared folders. Each WU, WP, governance body has a dedicated folder where also minutes are stored.

4.7. Reporting

4.7.1. Six-Month monitoring report

RESILIENCE PPP consortium partners agreed to adopt a financial and effort monitoring system which is the subject of D6.2 Templates and guidelines for the monitoring, reporting and management activities.

4.7.2. Periodic Report

According to the Grant Agreement, RESILIENCE PPP will submit three periodic reports, sixty days after the end of each reporting period (M12, M30, M48). The template of the report will be offered in due time by the European Commission through its web portal, but it is not clear if the Commission will use the same template as in the previous Work Programme, so there is no template available to be included in the present deliverable.

5. Control of the DOP

The DOP is a living document which may be updated to take account of new information and changed requirements, and whenever requested by the REA.

The RESILIENCE PPP PC is in charge to revise and update the DOP as appropriate.

6. Glossary

Term	Definition
Baseline	A significant state within the history of any planned activity
Best Practice	Proven Activities or Processes that have been successfully used by multiple Organisations.
Blocking problem	A problem for which no workaround solution is available at the time of the discovery and which prevents the normal use of the product or of a main functionality
Board of Directors	Composed by the General Executive Director and two Deputy Directors. It is responsible for further refining statutes, policies and strategies, oversees the implementation of the agreed-upon work plan through Units and may initiate ad-hoc working groups.
Change Request (CR)	A general term for any request from a stakeholder to change an artefact or process. A change request can be an Enhancement Requests or a Defect
Deliverable	The item (e.g. report, software, plan, site) which is the result of a number of tasks or activities conducted within the project and its Work Packages. It is usually offered to internal and external bodies (e.g. BoD, REA, EC), for review or acceptance purposes.
Effort	Effort refers to the number of labor units required to complete a task or activity. It is usually expressed with time units (days, hours, minutes) or their monetary value.
Escalation	Process that pass information and/or requesting action on an incident, problem or change to more senior staff (hierarchical escalation)
European Research Infrastructures Consortium (ERIC)	It is a specific legal form that facilitates the establishment and operation of Research Infrastructures with European interest.
European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures (ESFRI)	It is a forum composed by representatives of EU Members States/Associated Countries which is in charge of developing the scientific integration of European Research Infrastructures. It evaluates RIs willing to enter the European research infrastructures framework and its Roadmaps provide guidance for further development.
FAIR Guiding Principles	Guidelines to improve the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital assets (https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/).
General Assembly	Composed of representatives of the partners of the consortium. It is the ultimate decision-making body deciding on strategic issues such as membership and the overall budget.
Grant Agreement	Contract signed between the Commission and the RESILIENCE PPP consortium
Information System	A system, whether automated or manual, that comprises people, machines, and/or methods organised to collect, process, transmit, and disseminate data that represent intermediate of final outputs of business processes.
Issue	An event or condition that has already happened and has impacted or is currently impacting the project.
Performance Indicator (PI)	A Metric that is used to help manage a Process, Service or Activity. Many Metrics may be measured, but only the most important of these are defined as PIs and used to actively

manage and report on the Process, Service or Activity. Pls should be selected to ensure that Efficiency, Effectiveness, and Cost Effectiveness are all controlled.

Process	Sequence of activities designed to accomplish a specific objective. A Process takes one or more defined inputs and turns them into defined outputs. A Process defines roles, responsibilities, tasks, tools, standards and management controls required.
Repository	A storage place for work products (artefacts) output during process enactment, such as requirements, results (i.e. metrics), object models, interfaces, and implementations.
Review	Activity carried out to discover potential defects and to assess the quality of a set of artefacts.
Risk	A possible event that could cause harm or loss or affect the ability to achieve the project's objectives. It is measured by the probability of a threat, the vulnerability of the asset to that threat, and the impact it would have if it occurred.
Risk Management	The process responsible for identifying, assessing and controlling Risks.
Service	A means of delivering value to users/customers by creating outcomes users/customers want to achieve without the ownership of specific costs and risks.
Service Catalogue	It is the collection of all information regarding all services offered by the RI.
Service Coordination Committee (SCC)	Composed by the WU leaders, coordinates and harmonises the work in the Units and represents the Units towards other governance bodies. The Units' leaders conduct regular meetings and oversee the implementation of the agreed-upon tasks.
Support Office	Located at the headquarters in Bologna, Italy, which includes an accountant, a secretary, and a communications officer coordinating and executing the public relations of the RI.
Web portal of the European Commission	Online tools for the management of the RESILIENCE PPP, available via login at https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/home
Work Breakdown Structure (WBS)	It is a deliverable-oriented breakdown of a project into smaller components. In RESILIENCE we split the project into Work Packages, the Work Packages into tasks, the tasks into sub-tasks. If needed, the smaller action indicated is the activities.
Work Package (WP)	A particular set of activities grouped under a common topic or theme. Each WP has a set of activities under a defined schedule and with defined deliverables, effort, and resource constraints.
Work Unit (WU)	A particular set of activities grouped around a common sub-topic or sub-theme of the related WP. The tasks enlisted in each WP are usually assigned to a WU.
WP leader	The WP leader is the interface between the BoD and WP team members. The WP leader is responsible for ensuring that a task is allocated and monitored to completion. The WP leader is responsible for ensuring that staff follow WP standards, and adhere to WP schedules.
WU Leader	The WU Leader is the interface between the WP Leader and the WU team members. The WU leader is responsible for ensuring that a task is allocated, monitored and realised to completion. The WU leader is responsible for ensuring that staff follow WU standards, and adhere to WU schedules.

7. Applicable Documents

Applicable documents are documents from which all requirements must be fulfilled in the context of the Grant Agreement, although they are not repeated in the present document.

ID	Date	Title/Reference
A1	16/12/2019	Grant Agreement n.871227
A2	21/10/2021	D8.1 RESILIENCE Governance, HR Policy and management and Access Policy (RESILIENCE 2YSEP GA n. 871127)
A3	28/08/2022	Grant Agreement 101079792
A4	06/10/2022	D6.1 Governance set-up proceedings (RESILIENCE PPP GA n. 101079792), which is a public document available on the RESILIENCE website.
A5	29/11/2022	Consortium agreement based on the DESCA – Model Consortium Agreement for Horizon Europe, version 1, December 2021
A6	18/11/2022	D6.2 Templates and guidelines for the monitoring, reporting and management activities, which is a public document available on the RESILIENCE website.

8. Reference Documents

Reference documents are intended to provide background and supplementary information.

ID	Date	Title/Reference

9. Revision Log

ID	Date	Nature of Revision	Approved by
01.00	23/12/2022	Final	BoD

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